

D1.4. Data Management Plan

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-centre clinical trial.

Deliverable D1.4 Description

A report detailing the data management plan (DMP) for the duration of project as an Output of Task 1.5. This document is the initial version of the DMP. An updated document is planned by the end of December 2025 [M24].

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
ACR	American College of Radiology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire (European Council for Nuclear Research)
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EC	European Commission
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	General Assembly (when within the context of project management procedure)
GB	GigaByte
GDF	General Data Format for Biomedical Signals
GTPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HE	Horizon Europe
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NEMA	National Electrical Manufacturers Association
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
OS	Open Science
PDF	Portable Document Format
PU	Public

Term	Definition
RDM	Research Data Management
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms
TIFF	Tag Image File Format
TXT	Text File Document
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
USA	United States of America
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The scope of this deliverable is to describe in detail the Data Management Plan (DMP). The DMP specifies how project outputs will be handled during and after the ThrombUS+ project. It identifies information about what datasets the ThrombUS+ consortium is aiming to acquire/generate and preserve, in which format and the data management lifecycle. Best practices in terms of metadata and archiving are described, ensuring that the data sets acquired or generated will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), in accordance with the Horizon Europe (HE) Open Science (OS).

DMP is a living document, and a finer level of information will be made available through updates, as the implementation of the project progresses. An update to the DMP is planned by the end of December 2025 [M24], while respective updates will be published in Argos/Zenodo during the project at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068584>.

1. Introduction

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a document that describes the necessary details regarding data gathering and/or generation and data handling, such as data storage, data processing, and data sharing, both during the project and after the project. Procedures described in the DMP follow the Horizon Europe Guidelines for Open Science^{1,2}. Some open science practices are mandatory and concern:

- open access to scientific publications,
- responsible research data management in line with the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability), by developing and implementing DMPs,
- information about research outputs, tools, and instruments that are required to validate scientific conclusion or re-use produced data,
- access to the results for validating the conclusions of publications.

ThrombUS+ consortium considers open science as a crucial facilitator for accelerating research impact by ensuring transparency of research, research integrity, and the transfer of knowledge to industry and to society in general. This DMP provides the baseline actions and strategies to ensure that project's outputs are in line with the FAIR principles and 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. Moreover, it will ensure consistency across the project.

Research data management is the process within the research lifecycle that includes the data collection/acquisition, data organisation and curation, data storage and preservation, data security and quality assurance. Moreover, research data management encompasses activities such as the allocation of persistent identifiers, the provision of metadata, the licensing and the definitions of rules and procedures for sharing. These processes ensure that research data management aligns with the FAIR principles, facilitating the reuse of project outputs by other researchers. Research data management and FAIR principles can be applied to research outputs other than data, such as workflows, protocols, and software. It is worth pointing out that FAIR data does not necessarily mean open data. Data can be FAIR, even when access is restricted.

A DMP describes the data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, generated, and processed within the ThrombUS+ project. More specifically, it covers the following topics:

- what types of data will be collected and/or generated,
- what standards will be used,
- how will this data be exploited, shared, processed and made accessible,
- how will this data be curated, stored and preserved,
- which tools and methodologies will be used to store this data and for how long,
- how are data restriction levels managed.

The current version of DMP provides an initial outline of the data management plan defining information on which data sets will be generated/ acquired, how they will be handled and made available. This document also addresses the ethical and privacy aspects, as well as some data security principles. This initial DMP is based on project's DoA and its current needs. Finer details will be available over the course of the project.

¹ European Commission, Open Science in Horizon Europe. Retrieved on 24 Apr 2024 https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en#:~:text=What%20are%20the%20open%20science,%2C%20as%20closed%20as%20necessary

² Horizon Europe Programme Guide, Section 16, v04 15 Oct 2023. Retrieved on 24 Apr 2024 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

ThrombUS+ DMP was developed based on the concept of the Horizon Europe DMP template³ and using the Argos tool^{4,5}. The DMP is a living document that should be regularly updated over the project's course, to adapt in changes and projects requirements, to new data regulations and/or changes in the consortium policies. An update on the DMP will be addressed in D1.5 due to the end of December 2025 while all updates will be published at Argos/Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068584>.

2. Background: Regulations, standards and best practices

To ensure data protection, interoperability, sustainability and compliance-by-design, ThrombUS+ project will follow several standards, regulations and best practices related to data and health data; the major ones are summarized below.

2.1. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁶ is a regulation in EU law on data privacy and security. It gives individuals control over their personal data and simplifies regulations for international business. Implemented in 2018, the GDPR applies to organizations around the world that handle data of EU residents. It grants individuals rights to access, rectify, and erase their data, and restricts how it can be used. The GDPR is considered one of the most stringent privacy laws in the world.

Some key considerations are:

- **Data Classification:** The GDPR defines "health data" as any personal data concerning a person's physical or mental health. This encompasses data collected through medical devices, clinical trials, and healthcare interactions. Since health data falls under the GDPR's "special categories" of personal data, stricter regulations apply.
- **Consent:** Consent remains a crucial aspect for processing health data. However, the GDPR acknowledges the challenges of obtaining informed consent for scientific research. Alternative legal bases for processing can be invoked, such as public interest in scientific research or fulfilling legal obligations (e.g., pharmacovigilance).
- **Pseudonymization:** The GDPR encourages pseudonymization, where data is de-identified by replacing identifiers with pseudonyms. This allows for scientific analysis while minimizing privacy risks.
- **Transparency and information:** Individuals have the "right to be informed" about how their health data is used for research purposes. Clear and concise information should be provided about the research goals, data storage practices, and data subject rights.

³ European Commission. 2021. Horizon Europe: Data Management Plan Template. Retrieved 1 Apr 2024, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

⁴ Papadopoulou E, Kakalettris G, Tziotzios D, Moa H, Hasan A. ARGOS: a collaborative tool to plan and follow your data. Zenodo, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3898249>.

⁵ Papadopoulou E, Bardi A, Kakalettris G, Tziotzios D, Manghi P, Manola N. Data management plans as linked open data: exploiting ARGOS FAIR and machine actionable outputs in the OpenAIRE research graph. J Biomed Semantics. 2023 Nov 2;14(1):17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-023-00297-5>.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), Retrieved 1 Apr 2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

- **Data minimization:** The GDPR emphasizes collecting and using only the minimum amount of data necessary for research purposes. This reduces the privacy risks associated with data breaches and unauthorized access.
- **Data subject rights:** Individuals retain several rights under the GDPR regarding their health data. These include the right to access, rectify, or erase their data, and the right to restrict processing. However, these rights may be restricted in certain situations to ensure the public interest in scientific research is upheld.

Challenges and considerations in GDPR related to medical devices include:

- **Connected medical devices:** With the rise of connected medical devices that collect and transmit patient data, ensuring GDPR compliance becomes crucial. Device manufacturers need to implement robust security measures and offer patients clear information about data collection practices.
- **Data sharing for research:** Sharing healthcare data for research purposes can be complex under the GDPR. Data controllers (e.g. hospitals) must have appropriate legal agreements in place with data recipients to ensure ongoing data protection.

2.2. Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA)

The European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AIA) is the first-ever legal framework on AI, which addresses the risks of AI and positions Europe to play a leading role globally. The aim of the new rules is to foster trustworthy AI in Europe and beyond, by ensuring that AI systems respect fundamental rights, safety, and ethical principles and by addressing risks of very powerful and impactful AI models. The AIA was adopted by the European Parliament on 13 March 2024^{7,8}, currently undergoes a corrigendum phase and is expected to enter into force after publication in the Official Journal of the European Union (expected May/June 2024) and will be fully applicable 24 months after its entry into force, except for: bans on prohibited practises, which will apply six months after the entry into force date; codes of practise (nine months after entry into force); general-purpose AI rules including governance (12 months after entry into force); and obligations for high-risk systems (36 months).

The European AI Office, established in February 2024 within the Commission, oversees the AI Act's enforcement and implementation with the member states. It aims to create an environment where AI technologies respect human dignity, rights, and trust. It also fosters collaboration, innovation, and research in AI among various stakeholders.

The regulatory framework defines different levels of risk for AI systems:

- **Unacceptable risk.** AI systems are systems considered a threat to people and will be banned. They include:
 - cognitive behavioural manipulation of people or specific vulnerable groups: for example, voice-activated toys that encourage dangerous behaviour in children,

⁷ European Parliament Press Release, Artificial Intelligence Act: MEPs adopt landmark law, 13 March 2024, Retrieved on 1 Apr 2024, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240308IPR19015/artificial-intelligence-act-meps-adopt-landmark-law>

⁸ Consolidated text of the Position of the European Parliament adopted at first reading on 13 March 2024 with a view to the adoption of Regulation (EU) 2024/... of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act), Retrieved 24 Apr 2024, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0138_EN.html#title2

- social scoring: classifying people based on behaviour, socio-economic status, or personal characteristics,
- biometric identification and categorisation of people,
- real-time and remote biometric identification systems, such as facial recognition.

Some exceptions may be allowed for law enforcement purposes. “Real-time” remote biometric identification systems will be allowed in a limited number of serious cases, while “post” remote biometric identification systems, where identification occurs after a significant delay, will be allowed to prosecute serious crimes and only after court approval.

- **High risk.** AI systems that negatively affect safety or fundamental rights, and they include:
 - AI systems that are used in products falling under the EU product safety legislation⁹, including toys, aviation, cars, medical devices and lifts,
 - AI systems falling into specific areas that will have to be registered in an EU database: management and operation of critical infrastructure; education and vocational training; employment, worker management and access to self-employment; access to and enjoyment of essential private services and public services and benefits; law enforcement; migration, asylum, and border control; assistance in legal interpretation and application of the law.

All high-risk AI systems will be assessed before being put on the market and throughout their lifecycle. People will have the right to file complaints about AI systems to designated national authorities.

- **Limited risk.** This refers to the risks associated with lack of transparency in AI usage. The AI Act introduces specific transparency obligations to ensure that humans are informed when necessary, fostering trust. For instance, when using AI systems such as chatbots, humans should be made aware that they are interacting with a machine so they can take an informed decision to continue or step back. Providers will also have to ensure that AI-generated content is identifiable. AI-generated text published with the purpose to inform the public on matters of public interest must be labelled as artificially generated. This also applies to audio and video content constituting deep fakes.
- **Minimal risk.** The AI Act allows the free use of minimal-risk AI. This includes applications such as AI-enabled video games or spam filters.

ThrombUS+ plans innovation in medical devices thus involved AI falls into the high-risk category. High-risk AI systems will be subject to strict obligations before they can be put on the market:

- adequate risk assessment and mitigation systems,
- high quality of the datasets feeding the system to minimise risks and discriminatory outcomes,
- logging of activity to ensure traceability of results,
- detailed documentation providing all information necessary on the system and its purpose for authorities to assess its compliance,
- clear and adequate information to the deployer,
- appropriate human oversight measures to minimise risk, and
- high level of robustness, security, and accuracy.

⁹ Consolidated text: Directive 2001/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 December 2001 on general product safety (Text with EEA relevance), in force, Retrieved 1 Apr 2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02001L0095-20100101>

2.3. European Health Data Space (EHDS)

The European Health Data Space is a health specific ecosystem comprised of rules, common standards and practices, infrastructures and a governance framework that aims at:

1. empowering individuals through increased digital access to and control of their **electronic personal health data**, at national level and EU-wide.
2. fostering a single market for electronic health record systems, relevant medical devices, and high-risk AI systems.
3. providing a trustworthy and efficient set-up for the **use of health data** for research, innovation, policy-making and regulatory activities (secondary use of data).

On 15 March 2024 political agreement reached between the European Parliament and the Council of the EU on the European Health Data Space (EHDS), one of the central building blocks of a strong European Health Union.

The agreement reached by the co-legislators establishes clear rules for the use of health data for better healthcare delivery, research, innovation, and policymaking. The new rules will harness the potential offered by the safe and secure exchange, use, and re-use of health data, while ensuring full compliance with the EU's high data protection standards.

Under the new rules, citizens will have immediate and easy access to their digital health data wherever they are in the EU. Health professionals will be able to access the medical records of a patient when required for treatment in a different Member State, allowing for evidence-based decision making, in full compliance with EU data protection rules.

The EHDS also creates a strong legal framework for the re-use of health data for research, innovation, and public health purposes. The data will help develop life-saving treatments and personalised medicines, but also improve crisis preparedness, under strict data security and access conditions, and respecting fundamental rights.

The European Health Data Space, together with the GDPR, will give people the right to:

- Access their health data in electronic form immediately, free of charge and in an easily readable, accessible and commonly used format. Data can be accessed using patient portals, on computers or smart phones, depending on how the Member States make available this information at national level. For people with disabilities to be able to enjoy their rights, the access must be accessible in line with the requirements of the European Accessibility Act (Directive 2019/882).
- Share their data in electronic form with other health professionals when going to another hospital, without hindrance from previous healthcare providers or manufacturers.
- Add data to their electronic health record for themselves or for people who trust them, such as their children.
- Request changes to erroneous data online.
- Restrict access to their electronic health data or part of the data; in cases of vital interest, where their life is at stake, such data may however be made available with additional restrictions.
- Easily obtain information on which professional(s) accessed their data.

EHDS provides for primary and secondary use of data, the latter referring to use for research purposes.

Provisions for secondary use of health data include the following:

- The European Health Data Space sets out a common EU framework allowing for use of health data for research, innovation, public health, policy making, regulatory activities and personalised medicine. It will draw on the creation of a new and decentralised EU infrastructure for secondary use

of health data (HealthData@EU) that will connect health data access bodies which should be set up in all Member States.

- Those who wish to re-use health data will need to apply for a permit from a health data access body. The data permit sets out how the data may be used and for what purpose.
- The data can only be accessed and processed in closed secure environments to be provided by the health data access bodies with clear standards for cyber security.
- Only anonymous data can be extracted by the user who applied for the permit from the secure processing environment. Where researchers, companies or public institutions need access to personal electronic health data they can only access it in pseudonymised form, i.e. data offering information about the disease, symptoms and medication, without revealing to the user the identity of the individual. It is forbidden for the user to attempt to re-identify the data subjects.
- It will be forbidden to use the data to take decisions detrimental to individuals, to increase insurance premiums, to market health products towards health professionals or patients or to design harmful products or services.
- Health data access bodies will have to ensure transparency: information will be published about data access applications. In addition, data users must make public the results of their electronic health data uses and inform the health data access bodies of any significant findings relevant for the health of individuals.
- For simple cases, users can directly request data from a single health data provider as long as the same safeguards for privacy and security are ensured.
- Researchers and innovators from third countries can access data for secondary use under the same conditions and requirements as those from inside the EU.
- All Member States will be required to participate in the EU-infrastructure for secondary use (HealthData@EU) to facilitate cross-border studies.

2.4. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principle

The FAIR principles provide a set of guidelines for managing data, specifically scientific research data, to make it more discoverable, accessible, and ultimately reusable. First introduced in 2016, FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable¹⁰.

Findability emphasizes the ease with which data can be located. This involves using clear and consistent naming conventions, along with rich metadata that describes the data in detail. Such metadata should include things like the creator, creation date, format, and a description of what the data represents. Important steps to make data findable include:

- assignment of a globally unique and persistent identifier,
- data description with rich metadata,
- clear and explicit inclusion of the global, unique identifier in the metadata, and

¹⁰ Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, Boiten JW, da Silva Santos LB, Bourne PE, Bouwman J, Brookes AJ, Clark T, Crosas M, Dillo I, Dumon O, Edmunds S, Evelo CT, Finkers R, Gonzalez-Beltran A, Gray AJ, Groth P, Goble C, Grethe JS, Heringa J, 't Hoen PA, Hooft R, Kuhn T, Kok R, Kok J, Lusher SJ, Martone ME, Mons A, Packer AL, Persson B, Rocca-Serra P, Roos M, van Schaik R, Sansone SA, Schultes E, Sengstag T, Slater T, Strawn G, Swertz MA, Thompson M, van der Lei J, van Mulligen E, Velterop J, Waagmeester A, Wittenburg P, Wolstencroft K, Zhao J, Mons B. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data*. 2016 Mar 15;3:160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18> Erratum in: *Sci Data*. 2019 Mar 19;6(1):6.

- registration or indexing of (meta)data in a searchable resource.

Accessibility underscores the necessity of ensuring that data can be accessed by a wide range of users, including those with disabilities, and promoting open access whenever possible. This involves use of standardized (meta)data formats and communication protocols, focusing on open, free, and universally implemented solutions.

Interoperability highlights the need for data to be compatible with different systems and platforms, facilitating seamless integration and exchange. This involves the following:

- (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation,
- (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles,
- (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Reusable data requires clear licensing information and documentation so that others can understand how it was collected, what it means, and how they can ethically use it in their own research. This entails the following:

- (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes,
- (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license,
- (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance, and
- (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

2.5. DMP and FAIR related tools and infrastructure

Amongst the richness of tools and infrastructure available to support data management plans and FAIR data, ThrombUS+ considers at this time those listed below to cover initial DMP generation and management and support FAIR requirements for project data.

2.5.1. EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aims to provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes.

This environment will operate under well-defined conditions to ensure trust and safeguard the public interest. EOSC enables a step change across scientific communities and research infrastructures towards, seamless access, FAIR management, and reliable reuse of research data and all other digital objects produced along the research life cycle (e.g. methods, software, and publications).

The EOSC is recognized by the Council of the European Union among the 20 actions of the policy agenda 2022-2024 of the European Research Area¹¹ (ERA) with the specific objective to deepen open science practices in Europe.

The implementation of the EOSC is based on a long-term process of alignment and coordination pursued by the Commission since 2015 with the many and diverse stakeholders of the European research landscape. In the initial phase of implementation (2018-2020), the European Commission invested around €250 million to prototype components of the EOSC through calls for projects under Horizon 2020. The European Commission

¹¹ European Research Areas Policy Agenda, Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024, Retrieved 1 April 2024, https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/1749203a-1622-474c-b39f-ab1b25e35cea_en?filename=ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

also launched an interim EOSC Governance to prepare the strategic orientations for the EOSC implementation post-2020¹².

ThrombUS+ consortium will monitor advancements in EOSC in view of adopting any relevant implementations.

2.5.2. OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE is the outcome of European projects supporting Open Science¹³. OpenAIRE is a technical infrastructure harvesting research output from connected data providers.

OpenAIRE was established in 2018 to ensure a permanent presence and structure for a European-wide national policy and open scholarly communication infrastructure, with strong involvement of ATHENA RC, the ThrombUS+ Coordinating Partner. Today, OpenAIRE is a Non-Profit Partnership (NPP) incorporated under the provisions of Greek Law (articles 741 onwards of the Greek Civil Code) and Law No 4072/2012.

OpenAIRE contributes actively to EOSC via an open scholarly communication infrastructure: a set of services and an active European network of Open Science experts who provide guide and support in their countries.

OpenAIRE offers several services that support data publication, management, discovery, outreach, interoperability and access:

- OpenAIRE ScholeXplorer: a service that accepts publications-data or data-data links from validated sources, for science and research actors, by building a de-duplicated graph and providing access to it.
- OpenAIRE MONITOR: a service that produces well-documented, timely and accurate monitoring indicators of research activities for funders, research initiatives and organisations, by creating personalised and on-demand online configurable dashboards.
- OpenAIRE CONNECT: a platform as a service that enables institutions, universities, or lead teams on a scientific domain, to easily create, configure and manage, their own customised web portal that collects and shares research outcomes of their interest to their audiences. The gateways could be public or set in a private mode.
- OpenAPC: an infrastructure that collects cost information on Open Access publishing for research academic institutions by providing in-depth analysis on cost trends across publishers, e-journals and books or monographs.
- OpenAIRE Metadata Validator: a service that checks a repository's compliance with OpenAIRE, for repository managers, by validating it against the OpenAIRE guidelines.
- OpenCitations: an independent not-for-profit infrastructure organization for open scholarship that provides open bibliographic and citation data for the scholarly community by using Semantic Web technologies.
- OpenAIRE UsageCounts: a service for content providers, research funders and policy makers, that collects and visualises usage activity of Open Access Repositories by using automated and standardised scientific methods.

¹² European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Retrieved 1 April 2024, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

¹³ OpenAIRE, Retrieved 1 April 2024, <https://www.openaire.eu/about>

- ARGOS: a service to support development and publication of Data Management Plans on the cloud that connect to infrastructure services via OpenAIRE, including ORCID, Funding agencies databases, repositories and Zenodo.
- OpenAIRE PROVIDE: a scholarly gateway that receives content registration requests and provides guidance for content providers by viewing a personalised, user-friendly dashboard that shows the necessary steps and status of the services to complete the process.
- OpenAIRE Broker: a service that allows content providers to complete and enrich metadata of their registered scholarly works with information from the OpenAIRE Research Graph (<https://graph.openaire.eu/>). It is a notification service which effectively fills your content with up-to-date information that you or your researchers may be missing, and which enables you to showcase the openness, FAIRness, usage, and links to other records.
- OpenAIRE Login: an authentication and authorisation platform that enables researchers to securely access and share common resources and services using their existing academic or social identities.
- Episciences: a web platform that allows researchers to easily publish and promote their early work (preprints), to Open Access overlay journals. Authors get early feedback, while earning credibility and attribution with no costs.
- AMNESIA: a service that allows users to anonymize their data by using data anonymization algorithms.
- Open Science Observatory: a portal that facilitates access to the Open Science indicators for policy makers, funders, organisations, by combining and visualising information from all over Europe.
- OpenAIRE EXPLORE: an open research search portal providing access to millions of interlinked scholarly works (publications, data, software), their citations and contextual information such as organisations, grants. Search and view all types of research outcomes, find repositories to deposit your research, and safely claim/link your research.
- OpenAIRE Graph: a collection of interlinked research objects that aggregates metadata records from more than 70K scholarly communication sources from all over the world for researchers, service providers, research managers and policy makers, by following a participatory approach.

2.5.3. Zenodo

Zenodo was launched in May 2013 as a result of joint forces of OpenAIRE and CERN as a catch-all repository for EC funded research¹⁴.

Zenodo is a multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN. Datasets, documents and other research materials can be located via the Zenodo search engine. Scholars from any research discipline can upload data in any file format. A digital object identifier (DOI) is automatically assigned to all Zenodo files. Zenodo is compliant with the data management requirements of Horizon Europe, the ERC and other EU research and innovation funding programmes.

Publishing in Zenodo supports rich metadata for data description. Once the metadata is approved, it will then be published in Zenodo and, consequently, integrated into the OpenAIRE Graph.

Zenodo today hosts more than 3.5 million published items, including publications (2.1 million), images (0.9 million), datasets (0.3 million), software (0.12 million) and other items, of which 97% are open¹⁵.

¹⁴ Zenodo Open Data Repository (CERN), Retrieved 1 April 2024, <https://www.eui.eu/Research/Library/ResearchGuides/Economics/Statistics/DataPortal/Zenodo>

¹⁵ Zenodo Most Viewed, Retrieved 24 April 2024, <https://zenodo.org/search?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=mostviewed>

2.5.4. Argos

Argos¹⁶ is an OpenAIRE open and extensible service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring, and maintenance of Data Management Plans. It is based on the OpenDMP open-source software and is available through the OpenAIRE Service catalogue and the EOSC. Argos addresses Open and FAIR principles and best practices and assumes no barriers for its use and adoption. It does so by applying common standards for machine actionable DMPs as defined by the global research data community and by communicating and consulting with researchers, research communities and funders to better reflect on their needs.

2.6. Domain relevant (meta)data standards

In the context of health care, the term data standards encompass methods, protocols, terminologies, and specifications for the collection, exchange, storage, and retrieval of information associated with health care applications, including medical records, medications, radiological images, payment and reimbursement, medical devices and monitoring systems, and administrative processes.

Standardizing health care data involves the following¹⁷:

- Definition of data elements—determination of the data content to be collected and exchanged.
- Data interchange formats—standard formats for electronically encoding the data elements (including sequencing and error handling) (Hammond, 2002). Interchange standards can also include document architectures for structuring data elements as they are exchanged and information models that define the relationships among data elements in a message.
- Terminologies—the medical terms and concepts used to describe, classify, and code the data elements and data expression languages and syntax that describe the relationships among the terms/concepts.
- Knowledge Representation—standard methods for electronically representing medical literature, clinical guidelines, and the like for decision support.

There is a wealth of healthcare data standards widely used to cover different aspects of data and data management in healthcare¹⁸. Some major standards related to ThrombUS+ data are the following:

2.6.1. DICOM: Medical Image Communication in Medicine

DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine)¹⁹ is a standard protocol for the management and transmission of medical images and related data and is used in many healthcare facilities.

DICOM was originally developed by the National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA) and the American College of Radiology (ACR). It is a registered trademark of NEMA and is governed by the DICOM Standards Committee, a collaboration of users across all medical imaging specialties with an interest in the standardization of medical imaging information. Today DICOM is widely adopted by all manufacturers of medical imaging and related devices and the respective software industry.

The DICOM standard supports five main functions in medical imaging: to transmit and persist images and related data between endpoints; to query and retrieve files; to perform specific actions like printing or

¹⁶ Argos Data Management Plan tool, Retrieved 1 March 2024, <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/>

¹⁷ Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Data Standards for Patient Safety; Aspden P, Corrigan JM, Wolcott J, et al., editors. Patient Safety: Achieving a New Standard for Care. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2004. 4, Health Care Data Standards. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK216088/>

¹⁸ Schulz, S., Stegwee, R., Chronaki, C. (2019). Standards in Healthcare Data. In: Kubben, P., Dumontier, M., Dekker, A. (eds) Fundamentals of Clinical Data Science. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99713-1_3

¹⁹ DICOM, Retrieved 1 March 2024, <https://www.dicomstandard.org/>

archiving; to support digital imaging workflows; and to provide high quality images for diagnostics. In digital imaging systems, these functions have the goal of enabling interoperability between hardware and software from different equipment manufacturers and software vendors.

DICOM data contains pixel data and other data related to the patient, the exam and exam device parameters. It may contain multiple frames to store multidimensional images and cine loops. Pixel data is compressed using common compression standards like JPEG, JPEG 2000, and lossless JPEG. Additionally, DICOM data covers several healthcare related signals, image and signal processing outputs, radiotherapy protocols, and other related data. DICOM data are assigned a globally unique identifier.

The DICOM standard provides several services that specify how data are exchanged, how and where data are stored and archived, and how data is retrieved in a picture archiving and communication system.

2.6.2. SNOMED CT (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms)

SNOMED CT²⁰ is a standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records (EHRs). It is developed by SNOMED International, formerly known as the International Health Terminology Standards Development Organisation.

SNOMED CT contains more than 360,000 concepts organized in 19 categories: findings, procedures, situation with explicit context, observable entity, physical object, staging and scales, body structure, organism, substance, pharmaceutical/biological product, specimen, physical force, event, environment or location, social context, qualifier value, record artifact, special concept, and model component. SNOMED CT also contains more than 285 relationships (including hierarchy, finding site, causative agent, associated morphology, procedure site, method, direct morphology, direct device, using, and more) that create millions of correlations amongst the SNOMED CT concepts.

2.6.3. ICD (International Classification of Diseases)

ICD²¹ is developed by World Health Organization (WHO) to support systematic recording, reporting, analysis, interpretation and comparison of mortality and morbidity data. The latest edition, ICD-11²² (introduced in 2011), allows countries to efficiently identify their most pressing health problems.

ICD-11 facilitates the comparison of health data across countries and time periods. It ensures data compatibility and reusability for various purposes beyond basic health statistics, such as treatment recommendations, resource allocation, reimbursement decisions, and development of healthcare guidelines.

Encompassing a vast range of healthcare-related concepts, ICD-11 includes over 85,000 entities. These entities can represent diseases, pathogens, symptoms, abnormalities, reasons for seeking medical care, social factors impacting health, and even external causes of injury or death. Concepts and respective codes are organized in a flat hierarchical tree.

3. ThrombUS+ data and data management approach

3.1. Overall data management strategy and principles

ThrombUS+ consortium's strategy is to ensure that project generated data provides value to partners in a sustainable way to ensure first project success and later support the transition of project's outcomes to

²⁰ SNOMED CT, Retrieved 1 March 2024, <https://www.snomed.org/>

²¹ ICD, Retrieved 1 March 2024, <https://icd.who.int/en/>

²² Harrison, J.E., Weber, S., Jakob, R. et al. ICD-11: an international classification of diseases for the twenty-first century. *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak* 21 (Suppl 6), 206 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-021-01534-6>

successful marketable products. Data creation, transfer, sharing and processing must be handled safely and securely within the ThrombUS+ project. After or externally to the project, data must be shared securely abiding to existing regulations, as agreed upon by the project data providers.

The following main principles apply for project data:

- Collected data will abide to medical technology standards were possible and appropriate.
- Data, metadata and processes shall be controlled and managed.
- The project consortium will heavily rely on input and guidance from regulatory expert partner VDE to support data management regarding medical device regulatory affairs, in particular requirements concerning data that have to be provided by a manufacturer for placing a medical device on the European market and the External Ethics Advisor appointed by the General Assembly to support and oversee ethical issues related to data and data collection.
- All partners are fully committed to abiding by the principles reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, protection of human dignity and human life, and protection of personal data and privacy as they relate to the project. The partners confirm full compliance with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that was adopted on 27 April 2016 and implemented on 25th May 2018, and applies on the protection of individuals regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. Whenever necessary, the consortium will consider opinions of the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies.
- All project partners (including the USA based partner EchoNous) will be fully informed and engaged with respect to relevant ethical issues, in order to ensure that they are familiar with the legislation in this area as it applies to all the countries of the consortium participants. The project plans several dedicated tasks to address fully all ethical and legal aspects. Namely,
 - T2.2. Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics
 - T7.1. Clinical studies initiation including ethics submission and registration
 - T9.1. Regulatory compliance monitoring and mitigation activities
- Personal data protection aspects: The project focuses on personal data, including medical information, physiological signals, medical images, related medical diagnosis, and demographics, that will be collected by individuals during the project (WP7) and processed (WP5). Therefore, the project performs collection, use and storage of Personal Data, and thus, the project must adhere to all aspects of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). During the project, we expect that personal data collection will include quite revealing personal data – for example, medical data and diagnosis. Such data and related regulatory compliance requirements will be identified in detail early in the project (T2.2). Even when pseudonymized/anonymized, such data may still have the potential to identify individuals and needs to be handled with extreme care. The resulting issues need to be addressed both at the technological level and in terms of norms for data sharing and data protection (using privacy preserving approaches in WP7). Research subjects will also need to be made aware of the privacy implications of the technologies, and the options they have for limited forms of data sharing (WP7).

All project personal data will be processed in a GDPR compliant manner. Special care will be devoted to relevant issues like the system of transfer, storage period, transfer, and obligations of all participants involved.

All personal data will be pseudoanonymised on the collection site.

Clinical study data can only be accessed by personnel authorised by the respective principal investigator for data located at each of the five clinical partner sites (or other sites that may be added

during the project as Associated Partners), or the project Coordinator for data that may have been disclosed at project level.

The project will only use private data during clinical trial deployment. This data will be treated as strictly confidential, with personal identifying information being stored separately from other individual-level data, such as monitoring information and other user inputs. Personal identifying information for Clinical Studies A, B1 and B2 will be completely removed, and the respective data sets will be anonymized. Personal identifying information for Clinical Trials C1 and C2 will be stored under lock and key at each participating centre: it will not be placed on networked computers, and a named individual will be responsible for the security of and all access to these details at each centre. Other personal data will be linked to this identifying information by an uninformative code (that is, the code will be arbitrary and will not contain, for example, numbers relating to participants' dates of birth or place of residence). Other personal data will therefore be pseudonymised and stored separately from patently identifying information. Nonetheless, the storage and processing of this data will remain subject to strict obligations of confidentiality and be used solely for analytical and research purposes that correspond to the aims of the present project. Specific security and privacy issues at system level will be treated in individual tasks. The platform and modules will incorporate specific algorithms to technically ensure privacy and confidentiality.

- Clinical studies ethical aspects: The Project involves personal data management, including demographics, physical activity, diagnostic medical images and signals and medical diagnosis information. ThrombUS+ will treat this data as private and sensitive. The same protocols as traditional medical research and informed consent will be followed for all human subjects who approved to participate in WP7 tasks and studies. Informed consent will also be asked from each participant in order to publish certain units of data that illustrate ThrombUS+ research findings and publish anonymized data as open research data sets.

In all clinical studies where human participants are involved, informed consent will be sought from each individual participating in the research, on an entirely voluntary basis, with the possibility of withdrawal at any time (T7.1). Volunteers who are not able to give consent will not be included in the research (see inclusion/exclusion criteria in Annex ThrombUS+ Clinical Studies), nor will we be working with any vulnerable population.

It should be noted that the research will pose very few risks to participants – indeed, the only potential risk concerns data privacy. In this regard, the stringent protections of European General Data Protection Regulation for 'sensitive' 'personal data' (Article 9, Chapter 2) will apply, as will the specific safeguards indicated below. Data anonymization, pseudonymization or any other privacy preserving approaches will be utilized in the relevant individual tasks (T7.3). Also, the consortium will look out to encompass any relevant regulation posed by the European Health Data Space (EHDS) very recently published.

All project partners, with emphasis on those partners who intend to use personal patient data or deploy pilots for demonstration or evaluation will request approval from appropriate national or institutional ethics committees (T7.1). This approval will be attained prior to the respective activities, during the initial phases of the project (contract signing phase and first 3 months of the project). In case of pilot deployments, the approval will be requested once the evaluation methodology is finalized and in any case before the proof-of-concept pilot deployment. The requests for ethics approval will contain an explicit reference to the project title and other specifics.

- The project will use Argos to develop, publish and maintain the projects' Data Management Plan.
- Project data will be described and published in Zenodo, thus being assigned globally unique identifiers (DOI) provided by Zenodo.

3.2. ThrombUS+ data and data management

ThrombUS+ has the following primary types of data:

1. data collected via the clinical studies planned in the project,
2. technical and validation data collected during technical development, mainly as outcome of experimental and validation work related to the research and innovation on ThrombUS+ components,
3. project deliverables,
4. project publications and other dissemination and communication materials, and
5. literature used in the project.

These different types of data are further described below with further information on specific additional data management considerations and data management implementation issues pertaining to each data type. During the requirements analysis and the initialization of research and innovation actions the need may arise for other data sets to be collected and used for AI training, experimentation and validation. Data management plans for any new data set will be presented in continuous updates of this DMP and officially reported in the updated version of this deliverable due in December 2025.

3.2.1. Clinical study data sets

The project plans 5 clinical studies in the participating hospitals (TAU, LSMU, GNP, CSS-IRCCS, HSV). In particular, the project plans 3 clinical studies for the collection of large image and signal data sets for training the AI models and other image and signal processing tasks; also, the project plans 2 clinical trials to assess the feasibility and the diagnostic value of the ThrombUS+ product:

- **Clinical Study A:** A multi-centre cohort study for conventional ultrasound image set collection to create a training data set for research purposes (image processing and analysis, AI training). Participants >3000.
- **Clinical Study B1:** A multi-centre cohort study to collect training data sets for research purposes using the prototype wearable ultrasound developed in the project to fine tune the AI model. Participants >500.
- **Clinical Study B2:** A multi-centre cohort study to collect physiological signals, lower limb activity and plethysmography measurements via the ThrombUS+ prototype wearable sensor components from healthy volunteers to create a training data set for research purposes (signal processing and analysis). Participants >60.
- **Clinical Trial C1:** A multi-centre early feasibility study of the ThrombUS+ integrated prototype in patients in the postoperative ward. Participants 25-50.
- **Clinical Trial C2:** A multi-centre, prospective, double-blinded, pilot study evaluating artificial intelligence driven automatic detection of deep vein thrombosis by the ThrombUS+ device compared to standard ultrasound imaging in patients suspected of deep vein thrombosis. Participants: 50-100.

Data collected in Study A will be made openly available as an anonymized data set to be used by the research community for further research and development involving medical ultrasound image processing and analysis. Also, it will be used for training and science awareness purposes via open data challenges organized by the consortium during the project duration.

Data collected in Studies B1 and B2 will be made available under conditions for verification by third parties of the validation of ThrombUS+ components.

Data collected in Studies/Trials C1 and C2 will be made available under conditions for verification by third parties of the validation of ThrombUS+ solution in terms of user satisfaction and diagnostic efficiency.

The complete data management plan for each dataset following the Argos/HE template is provided in the Annex of this deliverable and is available via Argos/Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068584>).

This data management plan will be updated to include respective detailed plans of any other data set the project may decide to collect (if needed) via further clinical studies.

3.2.2. Technical and validation data

Technical and validation data refers to experimental data collected during technical development, mainly as outcome of experimental and validation work related to the research and innovation on ThrombUS+ components. Such data will be described in further detail during the project and will be published in Zenodo under open access or restricted use licenses according to the nature of the component involved. In any case, metadata will be published open and include a globally unique identifier as provided by Zenodo, while data will be available (if applicable under conditions) for purposes of component validation verification by third parties.

3.2.3. Project deliverables

The project plans 56 deliverables. These include 26 public deliverables and 30 sensitive. Also, 28 deliverables are reports. All deliverables, irrespective of their type, will be accompanied by a report describing the deliverable. Also, all deliverables characterized as sensitive will be accompanied by a publishable summary.

Public deliverable reports and publishable summaries will be made available via the project website (<https://thrombus.eu/>), EU portal and they will be made available via Zenodo under Creative Commons licences (CC BY), thus ensuring FAIR principles are applied for their dissemination to the public.

Project deliverables apart from reports (e.g. software and datasets) will be published in Zenodo under open access or restricted use licenses according to the nature of the deliverable. In any case, metadata will be published open and include globally unique identifier as provided by Zenodo. To facilitate findability, ease of access and better organization of project's outputs, the ThrombUS+ community have been created (<https://zenodo.org/communities/thrombus/>). Project's outputs shared within the Zenodo repository will be available under this community.

3.2.4. Project dissemination and communication documents

All project publications will be made available as open access and published in the project website and Zenodo under Creative Commons licences (CC BY). Project presentations and other dissemination and communication materials will be published on the project website and Zenodo under Creative Commons licences (CC BY).

3.2.5. Literature used in the project

Background literature required to support the project research and innovation activities (e.g., literature (mainly articles, books, and internet sources), laws, standards and guidelines), as collected by the consortium members, will be available for all project members via the free and open-source reference management software platform Zotero. The respective ThrombUS+ Zotero group has been set in <https://www.zotero.org/groups/5360524/thrombus/library>, and currently is available only to project partners. Furthermore, each partner is responsible for providing only original files in Zotero that are protected by licenses that allow open access.

Annex: Detailed DMPs for ThrombUS+ Datasets

The following data management plans follow the Horizon Europe DMP template as implemented in the Argos DMP tool.

1. Data Summary	
ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A Dataset: Conventional ultrasound image/video sets collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT of lower limb.
Description:	Ultrasound images and video clips collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Finally image/video data is accompanied by the output of labelling by experts to identify structures relevant to DVT diagnosis. Data sets from 3000 patients (with or without DVT) are planned.
Tags:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.
1. Data Summary	
Kind of research output:	Research Data
Type of data:	Digital
New or re-using the data	New
Type of the dataset:	Observational. Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during routine conventional ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb.
Format of the data:	<p>Data collected will comprise of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – DICOM images/video and related data. – Patient demographics, biometrics, and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. <p>Processed data sets will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized images and videos in a commonly used format (e.g. tiff). – Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. – Image/video labelling data in JSON format.
Expected size:	200 GB or more.
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	<p>To develop a product.</p> <p>Training AI models.</p> <p>Use for training and science awareness via open data challenges.</p>
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).
Data utility:	<p>Researchers.</p> <p>Research communities.</p> <p>Education.</p> <p>Industry.</p>
2. Links between outputs	

	Does the described output support any scientific publication?	Not at the moment. The data is expected to support publications in the course of the project.
	Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.
	Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to train AI models developed in ThrombUS+ project.
3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI.
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive.
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes. Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes. Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ . If the dataset is larger than 200 GB (which is the upper limit for Zenodo in extraordinary cases, 50 GB normally), data will be split or other infrastructure will be considered (e.g. paid option in FigShare https://figshare.com/).
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	Yes. Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes.
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes.

		Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo.
	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API.
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	No.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Open.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes.
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	

	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CCO) or Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY).
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	Yes.
	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	Yes. Promote via data challenges.
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project.
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set
5.	Security	
	What security measures are followed?	None.
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.
6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	Yes (medical data and diagnosis, but anonymized).
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7.	Other Issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No.

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B1 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B1 Dataset: Ultrasound image/video sets collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT of lower limb via the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.
Description:	Ultrasound images and video clips collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT via the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Finally image/video data is accompanying by the output of labelling by experts to identify structures relevant to DVT diagnosis. Data sets from 500 patients (with or without DVT) are planned.
Tags:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data.
Type of data:	Digital.
New or re-using the data	New.
Type of the dataset:	Observational. Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb via the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.
Format of the data:	<p>Data collected will comprise of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized images/video in commonly used format (e.g. tiff). – Raw data from ultrasound probe in proprietary format. – Patient demographics, biometrics, and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. <p>Processed data sets will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized images and videos in a lossless commonly used format (e.g. tiff). – Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. – Image/video labelling data in JSON format.
Expected size:	40 GB or more.
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To develop a product. Training AI models.
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).
Data utility:	Researchers. Research communities. Industry.
2.	Links between outputs
Does the described output support any scientific publication?	Not at the moment. The data is expected to support publications in the course of the project.
Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.
Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to train AI models developed in ThrombUS+ project.

3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI.
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive.
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes. Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes. Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ . If the dataset is larger than 200 GB (which is the upper limit for Zenodo in extraordinary cases, 50 GB normally), data will be split or other infrastructure will be considered (e.g. paid option in FigShare https://figshare.com/).
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	Yes. Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes.
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes. Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo.

	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API.
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	Yes, ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes.
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	To be decided.
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No.

	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	To be decided.
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project.
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set
5.	Security	
	What security measures are followed?	None.
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.
6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	Yes (medical data and diagnosis, but anonymized).
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7.	Other Issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No.

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B2 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B2 Dataset: Physiological signals and lower limb activity measurements collected via wearable sensors from normal volunteers.
Description:	Physiological measurements (heart rate, body temperature, oximetry), lower limb activity measurements and lower limb electrical impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography measurements via wearable sensors and a set of labels for each set of measurements with information on the type and strength of lower limb activity, including participant demographics, collected from more than 60 volunteers.
Tags:	Deep vein thrombosis, activity measurements, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, lower limb.
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data.
Type of data:	Digital.
New or re-using the data	New.
Type of the dataset:	Observational. Physiological measurements (heart rate, body temperature, oximetry), lower limb activity measurements and lower limb electrical impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography measurements.
Format of the data:	Data collected will comprise of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized physiological signals from activity sensors, electrical impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography (csv, gdf). – Patient demographics, biometrics, and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. Processed data sets will include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized physiological signals from activity sensors, electrical impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography (csv, gdf). – Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. – Signal labelling data in JSON format.
Expected size:	Less than 1 GB.
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To develop a product. Training AI models.
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from normal volunteers in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France) and other consortium partners, e.g. Kaunas Technical University (Lithuania), ATHENA RC (Greece).
Data utility:	Researchers. Research communities. Industry.
2.	Links between outputs
Does the described output support any scientific publication?	Not at the moment. The data is expected to support publications in the course of the project.

	Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.
	Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to train AI models developed in ThrombUS+ project.
3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI.
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive.
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes. Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep vein thrombosis, activity measurements, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, lower limb.
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes. Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ .
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	Yes. Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes.
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes. Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.

	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo.
	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API.
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	Yes, ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes.
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	To be decided.
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.

	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No.
	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	To be decided.
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set
5.	Security	
	What security measures are followed?	None.
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.
6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	Yes (medical data and diagnosis, but anonymized).
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7.	Other Issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No.

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study C1 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study C1 Dataset: Ultrasound image/video sets, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, lower limb activity and evaluation reports by patients and healthcare personnel collected from patients recovering from orthopaedics surgery via the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype.
Description:	Ultrasound image/video sets, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, lower limb activity and evaluation reports collected from patients recovering from orthopaedics surgery via the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Data sets from 50 patients are planned.
Tags:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, activity, lower limb, evaluation reports by patients and healthcare personnel.
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data.
Type of data:	Digital.
New or re-using the data	New.
Type of the dataset:	Observational. Diagnostic medical images and videos, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, and activity collected from patient recovering from surgery.
Format of the data:	Data collected will comprise of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized images/video in commonly used format (e.g. tiff). – Light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography and activity signals (csv, gdf). – Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. – Patient/personnel evaluation reports (txt, pdf).
Expected size:	10 GB.
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To develop a product.
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from patients recovering from orthopaedic surgery in the respective clinics of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).
Data utility:	Researchers. Research communities. Industry.
2.	Links between outputs
Does the described output support any scientific publication?	Not at the moment. The data is expected to support publications in the course of the project.
Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.
Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to train AI models developed in ThrombUS+ project.
3.	FAIR practices
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI.
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive.
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes. Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, activity, lower limb, evaluation reports by patients and healthcare personnel.
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes. Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ .
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	Yes. Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes.
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes. Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo.
	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API.

	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	Yes, ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes.
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	To be decided.
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No.
	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	To be decided.

	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project.
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set
5.	Security	
	What security measures are followed?	None.
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.
6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	Yes (medical data and diagnosis, but anonymized).
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7.	Other Issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No.

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study C2 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study C2 Dataset: Ultrasound image/video sets collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT of lower limb via conventional ultrasound imaging and the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.
Description:	Ultrasound images and video clips collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT via conventional ultrasound imaging and the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Finally image/video data is accompanying by the output of labelling by experts to identify structures relevant to DVT diagnosis. Data sets from 200 patients (with or without DVT) are planned.
Tags:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data.
Type of data:	Digital.
New or re-using the data	New.
Type of the dataset:	Observational. Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb via conventional ultrasound and the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.
Format of the data:	<p>Data collected will comprise of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – DICOM images/video and related data. – Anonymized images/video in commonly used format (e.g. tiff). – Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. <p>Processed data sets will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized images and videos in a lossless commonly used format (e.g. tiff). – Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary. – Image/video labeling data in JSON format.
Expected size:	40 GB or more.
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To develop a product.
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).
Data utility:	<p>Researchers.</p> <p>Research communities.</p> <p>Industry.</p>
2.	Links between outputs
Does the described output support any scientific publication?	<p>Not at the moment.</p> <p>The data is expected to support publications in the course of the project.</p>
Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.

	Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to assess the efficacy of the ultrasound wearable component developed in ThrombUS+ project.
3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI.
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive.
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes. Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes. Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ .
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	Yes. Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes.
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes. Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo.

	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API.
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	Yes, ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes.
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CCO).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	To be decided.
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No.

	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	To be decided.
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project.
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set
5.	Security	
	What security measures are followed?	None.
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.
6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	Yes (medical data and diagnosis, but anonymized).
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7.	Other Issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No.